

PHOTOCHEMICAL STUDIES IN GELS. PART I. THE REDUCTION OF FERRIC CHLORIDE BY MANDELIC ACID IN LIGHT OF DIFFERENT FREQUENCIES IN THORIUM PHOSPHATE GEL AS A SOLVENT MEDIUM

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The kinetics of the reduction of ferric chloride by mandelic acid in light of frequencies 366 and 436 μ in transparent and colourless thorium phosphate gel have been studied. The reaction was found to be zero molecular and the velocity constant was found to increase with increasing concentrations of ferric chloride and in fact $\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} / I_{\text{abs}}$ was found to remain constant for a particular wave-length which increase with increased in the magnitude of the quanta absorbed. The velocity constant also increases with increasing concentration of mandelic acid and was directly proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation. The quantum efficiency was found to be very low. The results were compared with those obtained in thorium phosphate sol before gelation and in aqueous solution. The rate of reaction was found to be the same in both sol and gel states of thorium phosphate but in water it was considerably greater. The extinction coefficients of ferric chloride in presence of excess mandelic acid were measured in all the three media. A mechanism has been suggested.

Photochemical reactions in liquid as well as in gaseous phase have been studied in considerable details but in comparison very few reactions have been studied in gel or solid phase. As examples, we may cite the decomposition of silver halides in gelatine studied by a number of workers, notably by Eggert and Noddack (*Sitzungsber. preuss. Akad.*, 1923, p. 116; 1921, p. 631; *Z. Physik*, 1925, 31, 922) in wave-lengths 365, 406 and 436 μ and the decomposition of AgCl (sensitised by Ag) on printing out paper studied by Weigert (*Sitzungsber. preuss. Akad.*, 1921, p. 641) in wave-length 436 μ . But no worker has, upto now, made any comparative study of the kinetics of any reaction in both liquid as well as in the gel phase. It would therefore be very interesting if methods could be devised by means of which photochemical reactions could be studied in gel phase and the results compared with those studied in liquid phase. With this idea in mind, we started our work using some transparent and colourless thixotropic gel as solvent medium. The advantage of using thixotropic gels is that they liquefy on shaking which set again on standing for some time.

In the present investigation we have used thixotropic thorium phosphate gel which is transparent, colourless and firm as the medium and have studied a very simple reaction—the photoreduction of ferric chloride by mandelic acid whose kinetics in aqueous solution were studied by various workers, notably by Ghosh and Purkayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 827), Benrath (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 74, 115), Winther and Oxolt-Howe (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1914, 14, 196) and by Bolin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 87, 490).

We have studied the reaction in media of (1) thorium phosphate gel, (2) thorium phosphate sol and (3) water and have made a comparative study of the photoprocess under these conditions.

In aqueous phase, (i) the reaction is zero-molecular with respect to ferric chloride. (ii) The zero-molecular velocity constant increases with increasing concentration of the reductant and in fact, $\frac{x}{\Delta x / \Delta t}$ plotted against $\frac{1}{[\text{Reductant}]}$ gives a straight line. (iii) The velocity constant is directly proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation. (iv) The

velocity constant varies very slightly with increasing concentration of hydrochloric acid. (v) The quantum efficiency was found to be 1.06, 1.18 and 1.36 in wave-lengths 488, 448 and 390 μ respectively.

The reaction may be expressed by the equation,

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental arrangement was the same as was described by the authors in previous works (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B 32, 145; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 257) with a few alterations viz. (a) the source of light was a mercury arc lamp whose strength of current and voltage were maintained constant by means of a regulating resistance; (b) the reaction cell was 4 cm. $\times$ 4 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. thick and made of plane glass plates fused into one another with a stopper at the top; (c) parallel beams of light were obtained by means of a quartz cylindrical lens.

Reagents.—Kahlbaum's extra pure ferric chloride and Merck's extra pure mandelic acid, thorium nitrate, potassium phosphate (KH_2PO_4), potassium iodide, hydrochloric acid and sodium thiosulphate were used. For making solutions bi-distilled water was used.

Preparation of Thorium Phosphate Gel.—Thorium phosphate gel was prepared according to the method of Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587) by mixing 0.25 c.c. of a solution of potassium phosphate (22.0%) with 5 c.c. of a solution of thorium nitrate (48.14 g./litre), making the total volume in all cases to 6 c.c. The mixtures on shaking for 3 minutes and allowing to stand for 5 minutes gave a transparent, colourless and viscous sol which set to a firm jelly after about 4 hours.

To study the reaction in thorium phosphate gel, the reactants were mixed in thorium phosphate sol and allowed to stand in the dark until the reaction mixture set to a firm and transparent jelly. The "set" reaction mixture was then exposed to monochromatic light.

To study the reaction in thorium phosphate sol, the reactants were mixed in thorium phosphate sol and exposed, just after mixing, to monochromatic light. The reaction was stopped within 72 hours during which the sol did not set to a jelly. In order to prevent the hydrolysis of ferric chloride, a certain amount of hydrochloric acid was added to the solution of ferric chloride.

Measurement of the Velocity of Reaction.—Thorium phosphate gel, though thixotropic, liquefies to a very viscous liquid on shaking vigorously and so it was found very difficult to pipette out the exposed reaction mixtures at definite intervals. For this reason 2 c.c. of the reaction mixture were exposed in the reaction cell each time and the whole amount was taken out in a stoppered conical flask after a definite period and the ferric chloride was estimated iodometrically by titrating, in an atmosphere of CO_2 , with 0.0029N-thiosulphate solution by means of a microburette. The initial concentration of ferric chloride was determined in the same way.

The p_x of the reaction mixture was determined potentiometrically by using glass electrode. The p_x of different mixtures were kept constant by adding required quantities of HCl or KOH.

Measurement of Intensity.—The intensity of radiation absorbed by the reaction mixture was measured by means of a "Weston's photronic cell" and a sensitive galvanometer. The photronic cell was calibrated by means of a standard lamp (12 v; 4.0W), standardised by

means of a Moll thermopile and a Hefner lamp. The intensity of absorbed radiation was measured by noting the deflections when the light passed through (a) pure solvent *i.e.*, water or thixotropic thorium phosphate sol or thorium phosphate jelly and (b) the reaction mixture. The difference in deflections in the two cases gave the intensity of radiation absorbed by the reaction mixture. It is to be pointed out here that thorium phosphate sol or gel has got no absorption in $366\mu\mu$.

It was found that the intense yellow colour, produced by mixing mandelic acid with ferric chloride solution in water, became pale yellow in media of thorium phosphate sol and gel. The extinction coefficients of ferric chloride were measured in the three media by means of intensity measurements, keeping the concentration of mandelic acid greater than that of ferric chloride and the ratio $\frac{(M^{\text{Mandelic acid}})}{(\text{FeCl}_3)}$ constant. The extinction coefficients at different wave-lengths and different media were found in the following way: The deflections in the galvanometer were noted, first of all, with the solvent alone and secondly with ferric chloride and mandelic acid mixtures of known concentrations. The molecular extinction coefficients of ferric chloride were then calculated according to the equation,

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{c \cdot d} \log_{10} \frac{I_0}{I_t}$$

where ϵ = molecular extinction coefficient,

c = concentration of ferric chloride in g. mols per litre,

d = thickness of the reaction cell in cm. and

I_0, I_t are the incident and transmitted radiations measured.

The extinction coefficients of ferric chloride were also measured in presence of varying quantities of thorium nitrate. The results are tabulated in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

λ	Phase.	ϵ .	λ .	Phase.	ϵ .
366 $\mu\mu$	Aqueous	1629'0	436 $\mu\mu$	Aqueous	610'3
"	Thorium phosphate sol	106'2	"	Thorium phosphate sol	47'6
"	Thorium phosphate gel	106'2	"	Thorium phosphate gel	46'2

TABLE II

a = Conc. of ferric chloride in g.-mols/litre		b = " mandelic acid "		$\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$.	
$a \times 10^4 = 1'94$		$b \times 10^4 = 2'24$			
(Thorium nitrate) $\times 10^4$...	2'3	6'9	23'8	20'3	33'2
...	1663'0	1173'0	735'9	565'7	438'5
					366'2

From Table II we can see that even small amount of thorium nitrate lowers the extinction coefficients to a great extent.

The reactions which do not take place in the dark were carried out at 25° . The experimental data are recorded in Tables III to VII. The reaction was found to be zero-

molecular with respect to ferric chloride. In the given tables $\Delta x/\Delta t$ = zero-molecular velocity constant = changes in concentration of ferric chloride in 2% c.c. reaction mixture per minute in terms of c.c. of 0.0029N-thiosulphate.

In the tables θ = temperature; I_{abs} = no. of quanta absorbed per c.c. per sec. and a and b have their usual significance as mentioned before.

TABLE III

Determination of the order of the reaction,

Medium = thorium phosphate gel; $\lambda = 436 \mu\mu$; $\theta = 25^\circ$; $a = 6.23 \times 10^{-3} M$; $b = 7.4 \times 10^{-3} M$; $I_{abs} = 300.7 \times 10^{13}$; $\rho_H = 1.74$.

	Time.	0.0029N-thio for a c.c. reac- tion mixture.	$\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3$.
1	0 min.	4.30	7.67 (from 1 and 2)
2	60	3.84	7.58 (from 1 and 3)
3	120	3.39	7.63 (mean)

TABLE IV

Effect of varying the concentration of mandelic acid.

Medium = thorium phosphate gel; $\theta = 25^\circ$; $\rho_H = 1.74$; γ = quantum efficiency.

	λ ($\mu\mu$)	$a \times 10^3$ (mol)	$b \times 10^3$ (mol)	$I_{abs} \times 10^{-13}$	$\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3$	$\frac{\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3}{I_{abs}}$	γ .
	366	6.22	7.7	110.1	3.7	3.4	0.05
	"	"	7.4	120.9	4.7	3.9	0.06
	"	"	14.8	122.2	5.3	4.4	0.07
	436	6.23	7.7	231.9	4.0	1.7	0.03
	"	"	7.4	300.7	7.6	2.5	0.04
	"	"	11.1	339.3	9.0	2.6	0.04
	"	"	14.8	343.7	9.5	2.8	0.04

TABLE V

Effect of varying the concentration of ferric chloride.

Medium = thorium phosphate gel; $\theta = 25^\circ$; $\rho_H = 1.74$.

λ ($\mu\mu$)	$a \times 10^3$ (mol)	$b \times 10^3$ (mol)	$I_{abs} \times 10^{-13}$	$\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3$	$\frac{\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3}{I_{abs}}$	γ .
366	3.11	7.4	76.3	3.0	3.9	0.06
"	6.22	"	120.9	4.7	3.9	0.06
"	9.33	"	128.5	5.2	4.0	0.06
436	3.11	7.4	206.2	4.6	2.2	0.03
"	6.22	"	300.7	7.6	2.5	0.04
"	9.33	"	355.0	8.4	2.4	0.04
"	12.44	"	385.8	9.0	2.3	0.03

TABLE VI

Effect of varying the intensity of absorbed radiation.

Medium = thorium phosphate gel; $\theta = 25^\circ$; $\rho_H = 1.74$.

λ ($\mu\mu$)	$a \times 10^3$ (mol)	$b \times 10^3$ (mol)	$I_{abs} \times 10^{-13}$	$\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3$	$\frac{\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3}{I_{abs}}$	γ .
366	6.22	7.4	120.9	4.7	3.9	0.06
"	"	"	76.3	3.0	3.9	0.06
436	"	"	300.7	7.6	2.5	0.04
"	"	"	186.1	5.0	2.7	0.04

TABLE VII

Effect of the nature of medium

 $\theta = 25^\circ$; $\rho_H = 1.74$; $a \times 10^3 = 6.227 M$; $b \times 10^3 = 7.4 M$.

λ ($\mu\mu$)	Medium.	$I_{abs} \times 10^{-13}$	$\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3$	γ .	λ ($\mu\mu$)	Medium	$I_{abs} \times 10^{-13}$	$\Delta x/\Delta t \times 10^3$	γ .
366	Aqueous	131.0	9.5	0.12	436	Aqueous	595.7	25.7	0.06
"	Thorium phosphate sol	120.9	4.5	0.06	"	Thorium phosphate sol	300.7	7.6	0.04
"	Thorium phosphate gel	120.9	4.7	0.06	"	Thorium phosphate gel	300.7	7.6	0.04

DISCUSSION

The reaction has the following characteristics:

(a) The reaction is zero-molecular with respect to ferric chloride. (b) The zero-molecular velocity constant increases with increasing concentration of mandelic acid. (c) The quantum efficiency is less than unity. (d) The zero-molecular velocity constant is directly proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation. (e) The velocity constant increases with increasing concentration of ferric chloride. In fact $\Delta x/\Delta t \cdot 10^{18}/I_{\text{obs}}$ remains always constant for a particular wave-length but increases with increase in the magnitude of the quanta absorbed. (f) The rate of reaction is the same in medium of thorium phosphate sol, before and after gelation, whereas it is much greater in pure water as medium.

On the observations made by Kistler (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 815) that the dielectric constants of thixotropic sols remain the same before and after gelation and also on the observations made by Heymann (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 82, 462) that there is no change in volume of thixotropic sols after gelation so that the average distance between the constituent particles does not alter, we can explain the reason for the same rate of reaction in thorium phosphate sol, before and after gelation, by assuming that the activated ferric ion deactivates to the same extent in media of both thorium phosphate sol and gel.

The quicker reaction in water may be due to a complex formation between mandelic acid and ferric chloride as is evidenced by the deep yellow colour of the mixture.

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